

ASTRAL POOL OF TECHNOLOGIES: DIGITAL TWINS TO SUPPORT MULTI TROPHIC AQUACULTURE WITHIN THE ATLANTIC AREA

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Introduction

Aquaculture is a fast-growing economic activity to boost sources of animal proteins worldwide, leading to significant industry investment¹. The project All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) focuses on integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) farming to support and promote sustainable aquaculture production across the Atlantic area. IMTA applications are exposed to many threats from external factors, such as climate change, increased risk of diseases², parasites and Harmful Algae Blooms (HABs)³. These activities also experience production and infrastructure risks from extreme weather events, changes in critical water physicochemical parameters (e.g. nutrients, temperature and dissolved oxygen). Besides, microplastics – an emerging pollutant – need to be carefully monitored because of impacts such as ingestion or filtration by aquatic fauna⁴.

Supporting sustainable IMTA activities within the Atlantic area calls for a complete technological suite to best address end-user needs. The ASTRAL pool of technologies aims at supporting these activities through a set of innovative components, including an Artificial Intelligence (AI) data analytics platform, emerging sensors, cost-effective Internet of Things (IoT) kits, off-the-shelf cameras and hardware solutions. All technologies embed some form of intelligence with advanced deep neural networks trained and validated in relevant environment spanning across Brazil, South Africa, Scotland, Ireland and Argentina. The present abstract showcases such a pool of technologies and its associated benefits to IMTA applications.

Aquaculture Digital Twins

The ASTRAL project proposes developing a set of technologies to support IMTA applications. It aims to pilot emerging sensor technologies coupled with IoT/AI solutions to help and improve aquaculture activities while monitoring the surrounding

¹ FAO. 2018. The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2018 - Meeting the sustainable development goals. Rome. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO

² FAO & World Bank. 2015. Aquaculture zoning, site selection and area management under the ecosystem approach to aquaculture. Policy brief. Rome

³ Klinger DH, Levin SA, Watson JR. 2017 The growth of finfish in global open-ocean aquaculture under climate change. Proc. R. Soc. B284: 20170834. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2017.0834>

⁴ GESAMP. 2016. Sources, fate and effects of microplastics in the marine environment: Part 2 of a global assessment, ed. P.J. Kershaw & C.M. Rochman. GESAMP Reports and Studies No. 93. London, IMO

environment. The proposed set of **Aquaculture Digital Twins** enables virtual replicas of the farming environment, species and facilities.

Cost-effective IoT Kits facilitate real-time aquaculture monitoring through multi-sensor twins for crucial water parameters (e.g., dissolved oxygen, temperature, chlorophyll-A, turbidity). The deployment at the aquaculture facilities extensively uses functional capabilities of long-range communication, optimised self-powering, improved software and sensor calibration models. Another type of monitoring twin leverages MEMS-based UV-VIS fluorometer-spectrometer to deliver complementary monitoring information ranging from nutrients to and physico-chemical parameters (e.g., ammonium, nitrate and dissolved oxygen).

AI Vision digital twins can benefit aquaculture farmers with automation to increase sampling capabilities and improve accuracy in visual-based inspection tasks. Work is underway to design and validate vision twins using cost-effective off-the-shelf cameras integrated into recent embedded AI GPUs for edge perception and processing in the aquaculture environment. The AI vision systems support macro-level animal biomass estimation on which AI models are trained specifically for multi-species fine-grained assessment of shrimps and urchins temporal profile growth. At a micro-level, the proposed AI vision twins provide a bench-top solution for HABs and microplastic monitoring, further customised with AI models trained for a diverse set of IMTA conditions (e.g. low to high water turbidity).

Considering that the IMTA is exposed to several risks, a holistic water monitoring solution is key technology to ensure optimised farm operation. Biosensor technologies based on bivalve behaviour are sensitive solutions for many of the events of concern (e.g HABs, toxic compounds) and physicochemical monitoring parameters. ASTRAL technology employs bivalve behaviour data coupled with AI models as "proxies" for water quality assessment. The biosensing twin uses either vision or MEMS-based inertial sensors as the underlying technology for AI model training and real-time inference.

The AI data analytics platform (AIDAP) aims at integrating all aquaculture digital twins to operate in real-time supporting end-user decision making. The AIDAP is an analytics off-premise (e.g., cloud-based) architecture that hosts multi-modal time-series sensor data, AI models and visualisation dashboards for the end-users. The platform enables anticipation of scenarios and events using predictive modelling of physicochemical parameters and biological water quality indicators built upon the latest developments in data science. The platform connects all the aquaculture digital twins via web-based API interfaces. Sensor data is fed into this platform to develop and improve data modelling algorithms.

Conclusions

The ASTRAL pool of technologies provides a complete digital twin solution for IMTA applications. Technology validation is currently underway to improve the technology maturity level in the relevant environment (IMTA activities in Brazil, Scotland, Ireland, South Africa and Argentina).

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